

Assessment of Clinical Profile, Mean Platelet Volume (MPV), and Platelet Distribution Width (PDW) in Thrombocytopenia**K. Hari Babu¹, K. Anitha², Ganesh Nallagonda³**¹Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, RVM Institute of Medical Sciences, Mulugu, Telangana, India²Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, RVM Institute of Medical Sciences, Mulugu, Telangana, India³Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, RVM Institute of Medical Sciences, Mulugu, Telangana, India

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Ganesh Nallagonda

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Thrombocytopenia is characterized by a low platelet count as a result of marrow hypo proliferation or peripheral platelet breakdown. Several diagnostic techniques have been proposed to identify the underlying cause of thrombocytopenia. The aetiology might include febrile illnesses including dengue fever and malaria, as well as other infectious diseases. The purpose of this research was to assess the clinical characteristics, mean platelet volume (MPV), and platelet distribution width (PDW) of febrile individuals with thrombocytopenia.

Material and Methods: Ninety-eight cases of both genders suspected with thrombocytopenia with acute febrile infections above 21 years of age were included. 5 ml of peripheral venous blood was collected to analyse the parameters including complete blood count, platelet distribution width, and mean platelet volume were estimated and recorded.

Results: The severity of thrombocytopenia was severe in 24.48%, moderate in 55.10% and mild in 20.40% of cases. The mean difference of platelet value, mean platelet volume, PWD, and PWD/PLT were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Infectious conditions such as dengue fever (30.61%), malaria (10.20%), leptospira (7.14%) and other conditions (52.04%) were observed in participants.

Conclusion: Mean platelet volume and platelet distribution width are the potential screening tools for diagnose and differentiating the cause of thrombocytopenia. However, Early suspicion, screening, diagnosis and prompt management of thrombocytopenia will effectively lower morbidity and mortality related dreaded illness.

Keywords: Febrile Illness, Thrombocytopenia, Platelet Distribution Width, Mean Platelet Volume.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Thrombocytopenia is defined as a condition where the blood contains less than 150,000 platelets [1]. Platelets are blood cells that lack a nucleus and are colourless. They have a crucial function in primary haemostasis [2,3]. Thrombocytopenia often causes mucosal bleeding as a result of a lack in primary hemostasis. The condition can manifest in various clinical forms and can be induced by a diverse spectrum of factors, ranging from mild diseases to severe syndromes with significant morbidity [4,5].

Various diagnostic methods have been proposed to ascertain whether a patient's low platelet count is due to reduced production or heightened destruction [6]. Bone marrow examination is considered the most reliable method for diagnosis, although it can be invasive, uncomfortable, inconvenient, and costly for patients. The mean

platelet volume is a non-invasive method utilized to evaluate a range of medical conditions including diabetes, metabolic syndrome, malignancy, inflammatory bowel disease, preeclampsia, and thrombocytopenia [7-10]. Thrombocytopenia involves an excessive amount of In addition, MPV has notable benefits in identifying the cause of thrombocytopenia because to its noninvasive nature, simplicity, speed, cost-effectiveness, ease of use, and reliability as a marker [11].

Multiple studies have provided evidence for the utility of mean platelet volume (MPV) in the diagnosis of thrombocytopenia [12]. Platelet distribution width (PDW) is an additional measure of platelet activation that reflects the heterogeneity in platelet size. High-grade MPV is associated with well-established risk factors, including

cardiovascular and cerebrovascular disorders, which increase the likelihood of arterial and venous thrombosis [13]. The objective of this study was to assess the clinical characteristics, mean platelet volume (MPV), and platelet distribution width (PDW) in patients with febrile illness and thrombocytopenia.

Materials and Methods

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of General medicine at from January 2023 to April 2024. A total of 98 cases suspected with thrombocytopenia with acute febrile infections attending outpatient department were considered. Cases of both genders above 21 years of age, suspected with thrombocytopenia with acute febrile infections, willing to participate were included. Cases under heparin treatment, history of malignancy with thrombocytopenia, undergoing

chemotherapy and not willing to participate were excluded. Written informed consent was obtained from study participants and study protocol was approved by the institutional ethics committee.

All the participants were subjected to detailed physical and clinical examination. Demographic details including age, gender, duration of condition, and details of medication were collected. Five ml of peripheral venous blood was collected under the sterile condition into the EDTA container. Parameters including complete blood count, platelet distribution width, and mean platelet volume were estimated and recorded. The collected information was analysed by using SPSS version 23.0. Data analysis was performed by ANOVA and $p < 0.05$ was considered as statistically significant outcome.

Results

Table 1: Sociodemographic and clinical profile of study participants

Parameter	Total no of participants (n=98)	
	Frequency	Percentage
Age (In years)		
21-40	29	29.60%
41-60	44	44.90%
>60	25	25.51%
Gender		
Male	34	34.70%
Female	64	65.30%
Infectious diseases		
Malaria	10	10.20%
Leptospira	07	7.14%
Dengue	30	30.61%
Other conditions	51	52.04%

Graph 1: Severity of thrombocytopenia among study participants

Table 2: Severity of thrombocytopenia among cases with infectious conditions

Severity of thrombocytopenia	Viral fever (n=47)	Leptospirosis (n=7)	Dengue (n=30)
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Severe	22 (46.80%)	01 (14.28%)	06 (20%)
Moderate	15 (31.91%)	02 (28.58%)	10 (33.33%)
Mild	10 (21.27%)	04 (57.14%)	14 (46.67%)

Table 3: Comparison details of study parameters among participants

Parameters	Platelets		Mean platelet volume		PCT	
	Mean±SD	p-value	Mean±SD	p-value	Mean±SD	p-value
Day 1	0.68±0.17	0.025	8.48±2.01	0.001	0.09±0.03	1.620
Day 2	0.66±0.10		8.13±1.65		0.10±0.03	
Day 3	0.64±0.14		7.77±1.26		0.21±0.04	

Table 4: Details of platelet distribution width and PWD/PLT among study participants

Parameters	PWD		PWD/PLT	
	Mean±SD	p-value	Mean±SD	p-value
Day 1	15.76±1.99	0.001	35.87±18.984	0.001
Day 2	16.38±2.14		31.30±17.14	
Day 3	16.06±1.89		30.05±18.26	

Discussion

Majority participants were between 41-60 years (44.90%) of age, followed by 21-40 (29.60%) and above 60 years (25.52%) with more female participants (65.30%). Dengue fever was reported in 30.61% of cases, malaria in 10.20%, leptospira in 7.14% and other conditions in 52.04% of cases (Table 1).

In cases with viral fever (n=47), the severity of thrombocytopenia was mild in 21.27%, moderate in 31.91% and severe in 46.80% of cases. In leptospirosis, mild thrombocytopenia was seen in 57.14%, moderate in 28.58% and severe in 14.28%. In dengue fever cases, mild thrombocytopenia was seen in 46.67%, moderate in 33.33% and severe in 20% of cases. The mean platelet volume was 8.48, 8.13 and 7.7, PCT was 0.09, 0.10, and 0.21 and platelets values were 0.68, 0.66 and 0.64 at day 1, day 2 and day 3 respectively.

The mean difference of platelet value and mean platelet volume were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) (Table 3). The PDW on day 1 was 15.76, day 2 was 16.38 and day 3 was 16.06. The PWD/PLT was 35.87, 31.30 and 30.05 on day 1, day 2 and day 3 respectively. The mean difference of PWD, and PWD/PLT was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) (Table 4).

Khan et al. studied 84 instances of thrombocytopenia, mean age 23.4±12.1 years, with female (54.8%) preponderance. There were 40 immune thrombocytopenia instances. PDW (59.1% and 43.1%), MPV (59.1% and 52.9%), and PLCR (50% and 52.9%) have inadequate sensitivity and specificity for immune thrombocytopenia screening [14]. The term thrombocytopenia refers to a condition that is characterized by a decrease in

platelet counts that are below the normal range, as stated by Erkurt and Mehmet Ali et al. (2012). According to the findings of the study, thrombocytopenia can be attributed to a number of factors, including insufficient platelet generation, active platelet breakdown, and variations in platelet distribution. "Pseudo-thrombocytopenia" is a phrase in particular that is essential to comprehend and comprehend completely. In the study, thrombocytopenia was found to have both acquired and hereditary causes; however, the prevalence of acquired reasons was found to rise with increasing age [15].

Sekhon SS et al., set out to examine grade platelet counts and thrombocytopenia. Thrombocytopenia was categorized as grade 1 when the platelet count was between 75,000 and 1,50,000/ μ L, grade 2 when it was between 50,000 and less than 75,000/ μ L, grade 3 when it was between 25,000 and less than 50,000/ μ L, and grade 4 when it was below 25,000/ μ L. Graph 1 shows that comparable results were seen in the current study, where 24.48% of cases had severe grade thrombocytopenia, 55.10% had moderate grade thrombocytopenia, and 20.40% had mild grade thrombocytopenia [16].

Fan X et al., reported that PDW was assessed on days 1, 2, and 3. The study concluded that measuring platelet distribution width on the first day of hospitalization is an accurate indication of the severity of haemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome [17]. The current investigation made a similar observation. Kaito et al., discovered that mean platelet volume and platelet distribution width are useful indicators for identifying thrombocytopenia. These indices demonstrate high levels of sensitivity and specificity. Kaito et al.

found that as platelet count decreased, both mean platelet volume and platelet distribution width increased. The parameters were investigated on the first day of the investigation [18]. However, the current study looks at the MPV and PDW values from day one to day three. Fan X et al., conducted research on PDW on the first, second, and third days. When it comes to determining the severity of haemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome, the researchers found that the PDW on the first day of hospitalization is a valuable signal to employ [17]. Sixty-seven percent of the patients who passed away had MPV/PLT ratios that were larger than 3.86 and PDW/PLT ratios that were greater than 41.8, according to the findings of Zainab Purbiya P et al. [19], who evaluated forty cases of thrombocytopenia with platelet count and PCT. Sixty-five percent of the people who passed away had MPV/PLT ratios that were higher than 3.45. The present study has limitations in terms of low sample size in different age group of the participants with minimal duration of data acquisition. Further studies are required to analyse the platelet indices in large scale participants with acute febrile illness and thrombocytopenia.

Conclusion

Mean platelet volume and platelet distribution width are the potential screening tools for diagnose and differentiating the cause of thrombocytopenia. However, Early suspicion, screening, diagnosis and prompt management of thrombocytopenia will effectively lower morbidity and mortality related dreaded illness.

References

1. Negash M, Tsegaye A, G/Medhin A. Diagnostic predictive value of platelet indices for discriminating hypo productive versus immune thrombocytopenia purpura in patients attending a tertiary care teaching hospital in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. *BMC hematology*. 2016; 16: 1–8
2. Mowafy NM, Elkeiy MT, Khedr MA-H, Mas-selihiy MHG. Role of platelet indices and antiplatelet antibody in differentiating immune thrombocytopenic purpura from other causes of thrombocytopenia. *The Egyptian Journal of Hospital Medicine*. 2019; 74(8):1732–6.
3. Norrasethada L, Khumpoo W, Rattarittamrong E, Rattanathammethae T, Chai-Adisaksopha C, Tantiworawit A. The use of mean platelet volume for distinguishing the causes of thrombocytopenia in adult patients. *Hematology reports*. 2019; 11(1):7732.
4. Subtil SFC, Mendes JMB, Areia ALFdA, Moura JPAS. Update on thrombocytopenia in pregnancy. *Revista Brasileira de Ginecologia e Obstetrícia*. 2021; 42:834–40.
5. Chauhan V, Gupta A, Mahajan N, Vij A, Kumar R, Chadda A. Maternal and fetal outcome among pregnant women presenting with thrombocytopenia. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol*. 2016; 5:2736–43.
6. Aponte-Barríos NH, Linares-Ballesteros A, Sarmiento-Urbina IC, Uribe-Botero GI. Evaluation of the diagnostic performance of platelet-derived indices for the differential diagnosis of thrombocytopenia in pediatrics. *Revista de la Facultad de Medicina*. 2014; 62(4):547–52.
7. Haile K, Kedir R, Timerga A, Mose A, Arkew M. Role of platelet indices as diagnostic and predictive biomarkers for comorbidity of diabetes and metabolic syndrome in southern Ethiopia: A comparative cross-sectional study. *Plos one*. 2022; 17(11):e0277542.
8. Detopoulou P, Panoutsopoulos GI, Mantoglou M, Michailidis P, Pantazi I, Papadopoulos S, et al. Relation of Mean Platelet Volume (MPV) with Cancer: A Systematic Review with a Focus on Disease Outcome on Twelve Types of Cancer. *Current Oncology*. 2023; 30(3):3391–420.
9. Bambo GM, Shiferaw E, Melku M. A mean platelet volume in inflammatory bowel disease: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Plos one*. 2022; 17(8):e0273417.
10. Walle M, Asrie F, Gelaw Y, Getaneh Z. The role of platelet parameters for the diagnosis of preeclampsia among pregnant women attending at the University of Gondar Comprehensive Specialized Hospital antenatal care unit, Gondar, Ethiopia. *Journal of Clinical Laboratory Analysis*. 2022; 36(4):e24305.
11. Arshad A, Naz Mukry S, Shamsi TS. Clinical Relevance of Extended Platelet Indices in the Diagnosis of Immune Thrombocytopenia. *Acta Clinica Croatica*. 2021; 60(4):665–73.
12. Rajantie J, Javela K, Joutsu-Korhonen L, Kekomäki R. Chronic thrombocytopenia of childhood: use of non-invasive methods in clinical evaluation. *European journal of haematology*. 2004; 72(4):268–72.
13. Kaito K, Otsubo H, Usui N, Yoshida M, Tanno J, Kurihara E, Matsumoto K, Hirata R, Domitsu K, Kobayashi M. Platelet size deviation width, platelet large cell ratio, and mean platelet volume have sufficient sensitivity and specificity in the diagnosis of immune thrombocytopenia. *British journal of haematology*. 2005; 128(5):698–702.
14. Golwala ZM, Shah H, Gupta N, Sreenivas V, Puliyeel JM. Mean Platelet Volume (MPV), Platelet Distribution Width (PDW), Platelet Count and Plateletcrit (PCT) as predictors of in-hospital paediatric mortality: a case-control Study. *Afr Health Sci*. 2016; 16(2):356–362.

15. Erkurt MA, Kaya E, Berber I, Koroglu M, Kuku I. Thrombocytopenia in adults. *Journal of Hematology*. 2012; 1(2-3):44-53.
16. Sekhon SS, Roy V. Thrombocytopenia in adults: A practical approach to evaluation and management. *South Med J*. 2006 May; 99(5):491-8; quiz 499-500, 533.
17. Fan X, Liu Z, Fu S, Sang J, Deng H, Li F, Zhang X, Li N, Han Q, Liu Z. Platelet Distribution Width at First Day of Hospital Admission in Patients with Hemorrhagic Fever with Renal Syndrome Caused by Hantaan Virus May Predict Disease Severity and Critical Patients' Survival. *Dis Markers*. 2018 Jun 19; 2018:9701619.
18. Kaito K, Otsubo H, Usui N, Yoshida M, Tanno J, Kurihara E, Matsumoto K, Hirata R, Domitsu K, Kobayashi M. Platelet size deviation width, platelet large cell ratio, and mean platelet volume have sufficient sensitivity and specificity in the diagnosis of immune thrombocytopenia. *British journal of haematology*. 2005; 128(5):698-702.
19. Purbiya P, Golwala ZM, Manchanda A, Sreenivas V, Puliye JM. Platelet Distribution Width to Platelet Count Ratio as an Index of Severity of Illness. *Indian J Pediatr*. 2018 Jan; 85(1):10-14.